

Electrode kinetics and formation constants of Cu^{II} with *N*-substituted derivatives of oxamic acid in aqueous media at DME

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Abstract : Polarographic technique has been used to evaluate the kinetic parameters and formation constants of Cu^{II} complexes with oxamate (OXA), iodooxamate (IOXA), *o*-toluidinyloxamate (OTOXA) and *p*-anisidinyloxamate (PAOXA) at pH 6.8–6.9 and constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.25 \text{ M}$) in aqueous medium at DME. The reduction of all these complexes is found to be quasi-reversible and diffusion controlled and the kinetic parameters (K_s , $D^{1/2}$, α) of electrode reduction of these complexes have been calculated and $E_{1/2}^r$ values have been calculated by Gellings method. The mathematical Mihailov's method was also used to calculate formation constants. Thermodynamic functions have been determined as the systems were studied at two different temperatures 303 K and 313 K. Results show that copper(II) forms 1 : 2, the highest complex species in solution with oxamate, iodooxamate, *o*-toluidinyloxamate and *p*-anisidinyloxamate.

Keywords : Oxamic acid, reduction, stability constants, electrode kinetics, Cu^{II} .

Introduction

Oxamic acid and its derivatives are biologically active compounds, essential for human being and their reactions with metals have good relevance to biosystems. They have good chelating ability with metal ions and also play an important role in pharmacy. Oxamic acid and its derivatives are used as thyroid receptor ligands. Substituted phenoxy phenyl oxamic acid derivatives related to L-threonine has cholesterol lowering and cardiovascular effects *in vivo* and *in vitro*¹. 1,3,5-Thiadiazolyloxamic acid amides shows hypoglycemic and antibacterial activity² depending on the character of the substituents bonded to the amide nitrogen atom. Ni^{II} complex compounds with oxamic acid have been studied by Sabina Zagan *et al.*³. Cu^{II} oxalate and oxamate complexes have been studied by Novosad *et al.*⁴. The complexes of Cu^{II} with wide range of ligands in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents mixtures have been studied polarographically^{5–10} and Cu^{II} has been found complexing with weak Lewis bases.

The reduction of copper(II) at dropping mercury electrode (DME) in aqueous medium has been observed to be quasi-reversible but in the presence of certain ligands it has been found also to reduce reversibly^{11,12}. The complexes of copper(II) with organic ligands in aqueous and

non-aqueous solvents mixtures have been studied polarographically^{13,14}, spectroscopically¹⁵ and by cyclic voltammetry^{16,17} by some workers. Electrode kinetic study of Mn with some amino acids and antibiotics has been studied by some workers^{18,19}.

Since iodooxamate (IOXA), *o*-toluidinyloxamate (OTOXA) and *p*-anisidinyloxamate (PAOXA) has not been studied with Cu^{II} at DME. The present work deals with the polarographic investigations of copper(II) complexes with oxamate (OXA), iodooxamate (IOXA) *o*-toluidinyloxamate (OTOXA) and *p*-anisidinyloxamate (PAOXA). The overall formation constants of the resulting complexes in aqueous medium have been evaluated graphically by DeFord-Hume's²⁰ method and mathematical method of Mihailov²¹. Since, the systems of copper(II) have reduced quasi-reversibly at DME which made possible to deal with the electrode kinetics of the copper(II) complexes and thermodynamics of copper(II) complexes.

Experimental

A manual polarographic set up was used for recording polarograms. The dropping mercury electrode had the characteristics $m = 1.145 \text{ mg per s}$ and $t = 3.16 \text{ s}$ in open circuit. Height of the mercury column was kept 50

cm. The measurements were done at constant temperature maintained by Haak-type ultrathermostat. Before polarographic examination, the solutions were deaerated by passing purified nitrogen through them for 15–20 min. The test solutions were taken in conventional H-type cell in one compartment, the other part contained saturated KCl solution. Saturated KCl calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The stock solutions of the metal ion and the ligands oxamate (OXA), iodooxamate (IOXA), *o*-toluidinyloxamate (OTOXA) and *p*-anisidinyloxamate (PAOXA) were prepared in double distilled water. The sodium salts of oxamic acid, iodooxamic acid, *o*-toluidinyloxamic acid and *p*-anisidinyloxamic acid were prepared at constant pH, controlled at 6.8–6.9.

All the chemicals were of reagent grade purity, metal ion solution was prepared from copper nitrate (AR) by dissolving requisite quantity of the salt in doubly distilled water. The supporting electrolyte used was KCl whose requisite quantity was used to maintain ionic strength constant at 0.25 *M*.

Results and discussion

The complex formation takes place as the following reaction

where *M* = Cu^{II}, *L* = oxamic acid/iodooxamic acid/toluidinyloxamic acid/anisidinyloxamic acid for 1 : 1.

The reduction of copper(II) for all the systems at DME in aqueous medium both in simple as well as complexed form were found to be quasi-reversible involving two electrons and also diffusion controlled at 303 K and 313 K. The above conclusions were drawn from the slopes

(34 ± 1 mV) of straight line plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs E_{de}

and proportionality of diffusion current and square root of effective height of mercury column respectively. Increasingly negative shifts in $E_{1/2}^r$ and decreasing diffusion current of copper(II) on addition of ligand, successively to solutions containing 5 × 10⁻⁴ *M* copper(II) and requisite quantity of the supporting electrolyte (KCl) to maintain constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.25$ *M*), confirmed complexation between the Cu^{II} ion and the ligands. The overall formation constants of consecutive complexes in solution were determined by DeFord-Hume's graphical

method and Mihailov's mathematical method at 303 K and 313 K.

For applying DeFord-Hume's method for stability constants determination, $E_{1/2}^r$ values of Cu^{II} in all solutions were first determined using Gellings¹² graphical extrapolation method. The extrapolation of $E + \frac{nF}{RT} \ln \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs '*i*' to zero '*i*' value gave the value of $E_{1/2}^r$ on $E + \frac{nF}{RT} \ln \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ axis. The formation of highest complex species is (1 : 2). The tentative electronic structures are

where *M* = Cu^{II}, *L* = oxamic acid/iodooxamic acid/toluidinyloxamic acid/anisidinyloxamic acid for 1 : 1.

where *M* = Cu^{II}, *L* = oxamic acid/iodooxamic acid/toluidinyloxamic acid/anisidinyloxamic acid for 1 : 2.

Mihailov's method was also applied knowing the stoichiometries of the complexes formed with copper(II) and OXA and its *N*-derivatives concentrations at 303 K and 313 K. The values of formation constants obtained by these two methods are recorded in Table 1.

The results of two methods show that the values of overall formation constants at 303 K and 313 K are in good agreement.

Thermodynamic functions values (Table 2) have been also calculated for valuable information regarding stability of the complexes studied.

The negative values of ΔG° show that the reaction tends to proceed spontaneously. The negative values of ΔH° indicate the exothermic nature of reaction process in fair agreement with increasing stability constants suggest-

Table 1. Overall formation constants of copper(II)-*N*-derivatives of oxamic acid (at temperature 303 K and 313 K)

Systems	Stability constants	Temp. (K)	DeFord-Hume's method	Mihailov's method
[Cu(OXA)] ⁺	log β ₁	303	5.4771	5.4730
		313	4.3010	4.2955
[Cu(OXA) ₂]	log β ₂	303	7.000	7.0030
		313	5.9822	5.9728
[Cu(IOXA)] ⁺	log β ₁	303	6.4771	6.4810
		313	5.9542	6.0211
[Cu(IOXA) ₂]	log β ₂	303	8.9294	8.9717
		313	7.9777	7.9030
[Cu(TOXA)] ⁺	log β ₁	303	5.9542	5.9690
		313	4.8450	4.8607
[Cu(TOXA) ₂]	log β ₂	303	7.9030	7.8981
		313	6.6812	6.6888
[Cu(PAOXA)] ⁺	log β ₁	303	5.8450	5.8895
		313	5.6990	5.7102
[Cu(PAOXA) ₂]	log β ₂	303	7.9777	7.9512
		313	7.6901	7.6989

Table 2. Thermodynamic functions values of copper(II)-*N*-derivatives of oxamic acid (at temperature 303 K)

System	Complex species	ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
[Cu(OXA)] ⁺	1 : 1	-34.0793	-7.5942	-87.4000
[Cu(OXA) ₂]	1 : 2	-37.0882	-9.7057	-90.3700
[Cu(IOXA)] ⁺	1 : 1	-39.8947	-8.9807	-102.0200
[Cu(IOXA) ₂]	1 : 2	-38.7729	-12.3809	-87.1020
[Cu(TOXA)] ⁺	1 : 1	-35.3137	-8.2557	-89.3000
[Cu(TOXA) ₂]	1 : 2	-36.6889	-10.9578	-84.9200
[Cu(PAOXA)] ⁺	1 : 1	-42.3143	-8.1043	-112.90
[Cu(PAOXA) ₂]	1 : 2	-41.8370	-11.0614	-101.56

ing lower temperature favors the chelation process. The entropy values indicate that complexation is favored by enthalpy and entropy factors.

Electrode kinetics :

The theoretical method of Gellings was applied for analysis of electrode kinetics which involves the plotting of log (Z - 1) vs (E - E^r_{1/2}) and Z is defined by eq. (1).

$$\log (Z - 1) = \log \frac{1.13}{\lambda \sqrt{t_d}} - \frac{(1 - \alpha)nF}{2.303 RT} (E - E_{1/2}^r) \quad (1)$$

where symbols have their usual meaning (*t_d* is the drop time). The plots of log (Z - 1) vs (E - E^r_{1/2}) according to above equation were linear (Z can be considered as mea-

sure of degree of irreversibility). The values of Z at various potentials were calculated by the eq. (2).

$$Z = \text{antilog} \frac{nF}{2.303 RT} (E_{1/2}^r - E) - \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (2)$$

From the intercepts of these plots, the values were obtained and *K_s* for electrode reaction was evaluated using the relation *K_s* = Δ*D*^{1/2} where *D* is the diffusion coefficient. The kinetic parameters, reversible half-wave potentials and diffusion coefficients values of copper(II) as a function of ligand concentrations are recorded in Tables 3(a) to 3(h) in oxamate, iodooxamate, *o*-toluidinyloxamate and *p*-anisidinyloxamate in aqueous medium, respectively at temperature 303 K and 313 K.

Table 3(a). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of oxanilate at 303 K

Total Cu ^{II} ion concentration = 0.25				
C _x (moles)	-E ^r _{1/2} (-V vs SCE)	D ^{1/2} × 10 (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	K _s × 10 ³ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.0890	2.4603	1.8825	4.7634
0.0015	0.0950	2.4044	1.4563	3.9985
0.0025	0.1020	2.4044	1.2872	3.4876
0.0040	0.1085	2.3485	1.1664	2.9638
0.0065	1.1150	2.2926	1.9263	2.8527
0.0100	0.1215	2.2366	0.9894	2.6734
0.0150	0.1280	2.1248	0.8625	2.1945
0.0250	0.1365	2.0130	0.7436	1.9673
0.0400	0.1450	1.9011	0.6542	1.8281
0.0650	1.550	1.9011	0.7963	1.9542
0.1000	0.1640	1.7893	0.6867	1.8325

Table 3(b). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of oxanilate at 313 K

Total Cu ^{II} ion concentration = 0.25				
C _x (moles)	-E ^r _{1/2} (-V vs SCE)	D ^{1/2} × 10 (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	K _s × 10 ³ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.0280	2.7958	1.4124	3.9489
0.0025	0.0380	2.6840	1.1556	3.1017
0.0040	0.0475	2.6281	1.0593	2.7840
0.0065	0.0530	2.5721	0.9778	2.5151
0.0100	0.0600	2.5721	0.9416	2.4219
0.0250	0.0760	2.3485	1.1380	2.6727
0.0400	0.8550	2.2366	0.8889	1.9822
0.0650	0.0950	2.1248	0.9145	1.9431
0.1000	0.1050	2.1248	0.847	1.8006
0.1250	100	2.0130	0.7945	1.5990

Table 3(c). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of iodooxanilate at 303 K

Ionic strength (μ) = 0.25				
C_x (moles)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	$K_s \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.1218	2.3485	1.8653	4.5973
0.0015	0.1285	2.3485	1.4704	4.1566
0.0025	0.1370	2.2366	1.2482	3.9805
0.0040	0.1465	-	1.1970	3.9067
0.0065	0.1565	2.2366	1.9306	3.8272
0.0100	0.1615	2.1248	0.9873	2.9806
0.0125	0.1690	1.9011	0.9283	2.9374
0.0150	0.1730	1.9011	0.8604	2.8603
0.0250	0.1840	1.9011	0.8037	1.9734
0.0450	0.1950	1.7893	0.7529	1.9081
0.0650	0.2070	1.6775	0.7945	1.8574
0.1000	0.2200	1.6775	0.7190	1.8163

Table 3(d). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of iodooxanilate at 313 K

Ionic strength (μ) = 0.25				
C_x (moles)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	$K_s \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.0760	2.5721	1.8160	4.6709
0.0015	0.0820	2.5162	1.3969	3.4367
0.0025	0.0890	2.4603	1.1452	2.8175
0.0040	0.0970	2.3485	1.1350	2.6655
0.0065	0.1049	2.3485	1.8800	2.7900
0.0100	0.1120	2.2360	0.9080	2.0300
0.0150	0.1200	2.2366	0.8889	1.9882
0.0250	0.1300	2.1807	0.7945	1.7325
0.0400	0.1410	1.9571	0.7846	1.5357
0.0650	0.1515	1.9571	0.8474	1.6589
0.1000	0.1620	1.9571	0.7477	1.6355
0.1000	0.2200	1.6775	0.7190	1.8163

Table 3(e). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of *o*-toluidinyloxamate at 303 K

Total Cu ^{II} ion concentration = 0.25				
C_x (moles)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	$K_s \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.1030	2.2900	1.5124	3.9876
0.0015	0.9600	2.2366	1.2556	3.2015
0.0025	0.1165	2.1248	1.1593	2.9203
0.0400	0.1240	2.1248	0.9897	2.7865
0.0650	0.1325	2.1807	0.9586	2.4952
0.0100	0.1395	2.0130	1.1590	2.7564
0.0150	0.1500	1.9571	0.9860	1.9978

Table-3(e) (contd.)

0.0250	0.1575	1.9011	0.9989	1.9563
0.0400	0.1685	1.9011	0.9476	1.8214
0.0650	0.1800	1.9011	0.8567	1.6892
0.1000	0.1895	1.7893	0.9674	1.7627
0.1250	0.1950	1.7893	0.8348	0.9863

Table 3(f). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of *o*-toluidinyloxamate at 313 K

Total Cu ^{II} ion concentration = 0.25				
C_x (moles)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	$K_s \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.0430	2.7958	1.8423	4.7859
0.0015	0.0490	2.7399	1.4061	3.5601
0.0025	0.0560	2.6840	1.1602	2.9432
0.0400	0.0630	2.6840	1.1274	2.8807
0.0065	0.0705	2.5721	1.8600	2.7230
0.0100	0.0770	2.4603	0.9460	2.7805
0.0150	0.0830	2.3485	0.8905	1.9856
0.0250	0.0940	2.3485	0.8026	1.8043
0.0400	0.1040	2.2366	0.7534	1.6874
0.0650	0.1140	2.1248	0.7207	1.5709
0.1000	0.1235	2.0130	0.8329	1.0637

Table 3(g). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of *p*-anisidinyloxamate at 303 K

Ionic strength (μ) = 0.25				
C_x (moles)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	$K_s \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.0950	2.2366	1.8345	4.5762
0.0015	0.1050	2.1248	1.4276	4.1306
0.0025	0.1140	2.1248	1.2453	3.9860
0.0040	0.1225	2.1807	1.1762	3.9148
0.0065	0.1300	2.0680	1.9105	3.8232
0.0100	1.1390	2.0130	0.9968	2.9706
0.0125	0.1430	1.9571	0.9374	2.9272
0.0150	0.1470	1.9571	0.8705	2.8064
0.0250	0.1585	1.9571	0.8172	1.9903
0.0400	0.1695	1.9010	0.7603	1.9284
0.0650	0.1815	1.9010	0.7986	1.8970
0.1000	0.1920	1.9010	0.7328	1.8106

From all these data recorded in the Tables 3(a) to 3(h), it is observed that the standard rate constant values are very close to one another indicating that the reduction of copper(II) in OXA, IOXA, OTOXA and PAOXA medium at DME go with the same rate. As the ligand con-

Table 3(h). Kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} in various concentration of *p*-anisidinyloxamate at 313 K

Ionic strength (μ) = 0.25				
C_x (moles)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	α	$K_s \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.0010	0.0680	2.9076	1.5236	3.9707
0.0025	0.0830	2.7958	1.1630	2.9870
0.0040	0.0880	2.6840	0.9705	2.7934
0.0065	0.0970	2.5721	0.9492	2.5093
0.0100	0.1040	2.5721	1.1623	2.8191
0.0250	0.1235	2.4603	0.9105	1.8354
0.0400	0.1330	2.2470	0.8634	1.7045
0.0650	0.1450	2.2926	0.9583	1.7709
0.1000	0.1550	2.2366	0.8492	0.9913
0.1250	0.1600	2.1250	0.78709	0.9104

centration increases (in all systems) the values of K_s also decreases in general but some irregularity is observed in Copper(II)-OTOXA system at 0.01 *M* concentration. This irregularity may be attributed to stereochemical, stoichiometric and thermal changes taking place during reduction.

A comparison of data obtained at temperature 303 K in each case clearly indicates that the rate of the reaction at DME is more i.e. reaction goes faster in each case but not with an appreciable difference. It is also concluded that the rate of the electrode reaction slows down as more amount of the ligand is added to the solution of simple metal ion solution, which shows complexation between copper(II) and the ligand OXA, IOXA, OTOXA and PAOXA.

From the values of overall formation constants of the complexes of copper(II) with various ligands, it appears that the order of overall formation constant values is :

There is difference in the order of stability of complexes. The above order of copper(II) complexes can very well be explained on the basis of mesomeric effect. Since copper(II) forms the highest complex 1 : 2, therefore the steric effect due to methyl group in OTOXA is not appreciable and the sole factor governing the above order of stability is the electron donating tendency of the substituents.

Thermodynamic functions values also are in the same order as the order for stability constants although some minor deviation may be seen due to different approaches for evaluating β_j values and thermodynamic functions values.

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